

SOCIAL INNOVATION FOR RURAL BIOECONOMIES

Duygu Celik^{*1}, Silvia Caneva^{*1}, Chuan Ma¹, Ingo Ball¹, Rainer Janssen¹, Holger Gerdes², Zoritz Kiresiewa², Nina Bailet³, Rafael Castillo Barrero⁴, Carmen Ronchel Barreno⁴, Emilija Mihajloska⁵, Katarzyna Rull Quesada⁶, Kristina Pammer⁷, Luise Dauwa⁷, Gabriele Wolkerstorfer⁷, Frans Feil⁸, Marisa Groenestege⁸, Barbro Kalla⁹, Magnus Matisons⁹

^{*}Contact authors, WIP – Renewable Energies, Sylvenstein Strasse 2,
Munich, Germany (www.wip-munich.de)
+49 89 72012726

duygu.celik@wip-munich.de

silvia.caneva@wip-munich.de

¹WIP – Renewable Energies, Germany, ²Ecologic Institute, Germany, ³Association of the Chambers of Agriculture of the Atlantic Area, France, ⁴Technological Corporation of Andalusia, Spain, ⁵International Centre for Sustainable Development of Energy, Water and Environment Systems - Macedonian Section, North Macedonia, ⁶UNIMOS Alliance, Poland, ⁷Business Upper Austria, Austria, ⁸B.T.G. BIOMASS TECHNOLOGY GROUP BV, the Netherlands, ⁹BioFuel Region, Sweden

ABSTRACT: The overall concept of the SCALE-UP project is based on a holistic approach to accelerate the development of regional bioeconomies and promote social, environmental and economic benefits for rural development. The project assists regional multi-actor partnerships comprised of private firms, governments, policymakers, civil society organizations, and researchers in discovering and scaling-up innovative and sustainable bio-based value chains based on regional resources. In pursuing this goal, citizen inclusion and the social dimensions of bio-based solutions cannot be ignored. This is where social innovation comes in and fosters sustainable development. With this in mind, the concept of social innovation has been analyzed within the framework of the SCALE-UP project and best practices have been investigated also in regional contexts. All the information collected serves as a handbook to provide a reference for regional stakeholders. This abstract reveals the key outputs of the handbook.

Keywords: Biobased economy, circular economy, sustainability

1 INTRODUCTION

There is an increasing awareness about how important it is to include citizens and social aspects in the context of rural bioeconomies. Without this dimension, the impact of any action of bio-based innovations in rural areas will not be sufficient. Social innovation can be seen as the boost for the adaptation of sustainable and innovative practices. This handbook has been developed in the framework of SCALE-UP project with the aim of providing stakeholders with guidelines for the identification of good practises of social innovation in rural bioeconomies.

The focus is on the stakeholders of the SCALE-UP project case study areas: Northern Sweden (SE), Mazovia (PL), French Atlantic Arc (FR), Upper Austria (AT), Strumica (MK), Andalusia (ES), and any activities addressing the research question of the SCALE-UP project: “How can social innovation increase the role of the social actors in a rural bioeconomy context?”

2 METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed in selecting social innovations for the SCALE-UP project ensures a comprehensive and replicable approach that can be adapted for use in diverse regions and sectors beyond rural bioeconomies of SCALE-UP. The systematic process of the selected methodology unfolds through a series of key steps, described in the next paragraphs, emphasizing a holistic understanding of social innovation and its application in the specific context of rural bioeconomies. Throughout the entire process, ethical considerations were prioritized. Informed consent was obtained from the interviewed stakeholders, and the name of all references consulted are included in this handbook.

- Literature Review and Projects Analysis

A thorough investigation of related studies, reports, and outcomes of sister projects and relevant initiatives was conducted. Reference projects included but not limited to: BE-Rural, MainStreamBio, RuralBioUp, SafeHabitat, ... Relevant documents, including deliverables, websites, digital platforms, and policy briefs, were scrutinized to extract valuable insights into social innovation within the bioeconomy context.

- EU Policy Analysis

The approach of the European Union towards social innovation was analysed by examining Commission's policy frameworks, funding-financial instruments, and social innovation ecosystems. This step ensures alignment with EU strategies and guidelines in the development of social innovations. The social innovation policy in the European Union was underpinned by three core frameworks: the Europe 2020 strategy (2010–2020), the Social Business Initiative, and the Social Investment Package. These frameworks served to provide coherence and organization to the implementation of social innovation policies. They not only outlined the specific objectives of social innovation initiatives but also contextualized them within the broader social, political, and economic goals of the EU (Nicholls & Edmiston, 2018).

- Scientific Publications and Knowledge Synthesis

A comprehensive review of scientific publications, focusing on academic papers, reports, case studies, and books related to social innovation, rural development, and bioeconomies, was conducted and listed in the references. This synthesized existing knowledge and identified key concepts, theories, good practices, and challenges in the field.

- Definition of Social Innovation

Following the collection of up-to-date information, a precise definition of social innovation was drafted (see chapter 3.1). This definition served as a guiding framework for the subsequent selection of social innovations in the six SCALE-UP regions.

- Project Partner Interactions

Continuous engagement and collaboration with SCALE-UP project partners played a pivotal role. Regular project meetings provided a platform to exchange information, understand regional needs, and shape recommendations for the handbook.

- Value Chain Investigation and Match-Making Process

The investigation of each SCALE-UP region's value chains was a crucial step, ensuring a tailored selection of social innovations. A match-making process was utilized to identify social innovations that aligned best with the specific needs of each region.

- Identification of Good Practices of Social Innovation

Based on the information collected during the previous step, good practices on social innovations were collected to draw insights from various social innovation approaches. This facilitated the identification of good practices of social innovation identified for the SCALE-UP regions based on their value chain.

- One-to-One Online Meetings and Feedback Round

WIP organized one-to-one online meetings with partners responsible for each region of the SCALE-UP project. These meetings included an overview of their value chains, confirmation of proposed value chains, approval of the definition of social innovation, and the presentation of identified social innovations. Partners provided valuable feedback, confirming feasibility, and offering insights into local implementation.

- Iterative Development

The development of the handbook followed an iterative process, with multiple drafts reviewed by the consortium. Feedback and suggestions were incorporated to enhance the quality and clarity of the content, ensuring a robust and collaborative final product.

3 DEFINITION OF SOCIAL INNOVATION

The definition adopted for social innovation in the framework of the SCALE-UP project is the following:

“Social innovation is an innovation that provides a valuable and sustainable product and/or service to the market and meets the needs of the society. Social innovation creates new relationships and collaborations among citizens and stakeholders, providing a sense of contribution and/or community, which improve the health and well-being of the actors implementing it”.

The definition elaborated for the SCALE-UP project combines the diverse perspectives of the investigated definition of social innovations into a comprehensive framework tailored to the goals and challenges of rural bioeconomies. This definition emphasizes the dual role of

social innovation in providing valuable and sustainable products and services to the market while addressing societal needs.

4 THE RELEVANCE OF SOCIAL INNOVATION

Social innovation can drive economic growth by giving companies new opportunities to innovate, create jobs, and improve their products and services (Wang, 2022). These added values can be exemplified as improved access to basic services, job creations, advancing environmental sustainability, fostering social inclusion and climate change mitigation. Those are some of the most urgent issues affecting society. Social innovation creates resilient and sustainable economic systems, facilitates the shift to a low-carbon economy, and improves social cohesion and well-being.

The concept of social innovation can be implemented in many different contexts such as energy, governance, public management, finance or social transformation. Mostly being applied in social issues, it also has room for technical areas to create new technologies, products, and services that address social and environmental challenges, while also generating economic and social value.

Otto et al. identifies in Social Tipping Interventions (STI) the solution to provide a fundamental contribution in limiting global warming to 1.5°C (Otto, et al., 2020). The scenario Share Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) 1.5°C (marked in pink color in the figure below, is the scenario that includes the Social Tipping Interventions and is the only scenario able to respect the Paris Agreement, blue square, in keeping global warming below 1.5°C until 2100.

Figure 1: Social tipping dynamics for stabilizing Earth's climate by 2050 (Otto, et al., 2020)

Social Tipping Interventions (STIs) are processes able to rapidly spread technologies, behaviors, social norms and trigger Social Tipping Elements (STEs). Otto et al. refers to STEs as “subdomains of the planetary socioeconomic system where the required disruptive change may take place and lead to a sufficient fast reduction in anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions” (Otto, et al., 2020).

5 STAKEHOLDERS

Stakeholder mapping is essential for ensuring a systematic and accurate identification of relevant stakeholders needed for the identified social innovation. It provides a structured approach to categorize and analyse stakeholders, developing a solid understanding of their roles, relationships, and potential contributions.

Social innovation stakeholder groups are described in detail below. According to the authors of this handbook, their role can be categorized as shown in the table.

Table I: Social innovation stakeholders and their roles (WIP Renewable Energies)

Stakeholders	Role
Primary Producers	Contributing to sustainable resource management, technology adoption, environmental stewardship, and knowledge sharing
Secondary Producers	Creation of value-added goods or services, additional economic value
Government and Policy Bodies	Policy development and regulation, funding and investment, infrastructure development, promotion of collaboration, monitoring and evaluation
Research and Academic Institutions	R&D, knowledge dissemination through publications, policy advocacy, entrepreneurship and start-up support
Industry Associations	Member representation, market development, certification, setting standards, networking and collaboration
Environmental Organizations	Regulation and compliance, technical assistance, education and outreach, monitoring and evaluation
Community Representatives	Voice, community engagement, conflict resolution, local entrepreneurship

6 GOOD PRACTICES OF SOCIAL INNOVATION FOR RURAL BIOECONOMIES AND MATCHMAKING WITH SCALE-UP REGIONS

Guided by the social innovation definition outlined in this handbook, which underscores the provision of valuable and sustainable products or services meeting societal needs while fostering new relationships and collaborations, this subchapter seeks to shed light on effective strategies and successful social innovation initiatives within rural bioeconomies. In doing so, the objective is not only to inspire and educate readers but also to provide actionable insights, problem-solving approaches, and tangible models for implementation.

Northern Sweden

Northern Sweden stands out with its woody resources, covers extensive forests that are actively managed for timber, paper and pulp production. The region is faced with the challenge of utilizing these resources effectively. That's why a particular emphasis is placed on extracting value from forestry by-products, thereby creating business opportunities, especially in rural areas where employment options may be limited. Proposed solutions for this region are:

- Local bioeconomy cooperatives to bring together all local stakeholders to enhance the sustainable utilization of local re-sources;
- Forest carbon credit trading platform where forest owners can sell carbon credits for sustainable forest management practices;

- Forest innovation grants for local entrepreneurs, researchers, and community groups to develop innovative products and technologies using forest byproducts;
- Wood fuel network to connect all actors within the whole value chain.

Mazovia, Poland

The Mazovia region is known for the production of new functional agri-food products but lacking bio-based packaging. Mazovia has a regional development characterized by concise and collective actions. The Radom region in Mazovia aims to harmonize agricultural prosperity and bioeconomic progress. Thus, the strategy developed for the region includes:

- Collaborative platform to bring all stakeholders and foster cross-sectoral partnerships;
- Bio-based packaging incentives that the local government and policy bodies could introduce to encourage the adoption of bio-based packaging among agri-food producers;
- Educational campaigns and workshops to foster a sense of environmental consciousness and engagement among locals.

French Atlantic Arc

French Atlantic Arc region has expertise and capabilities in hemp production and valorization. The region is also good at diversifying market opportunities through downstream conversion stages. It capitalizes on its strengths with defibrillation industrial units and on-farm processing facilities. Another focus of this region is bio-based buildings. Part of the population shows a keen awareness of the importance of bio-based construction, prioritizing the use of environmentally friendly materials that contribute to sustainable practices. To diversify market opportunities and its commitment to bio-based construction materials, proposed solutions are:

- Collaborative supply chains that connect primary producers (farmers and hemp producers) with the building and agri-food industries;
- Farm-Table partnering up to ensure surplus food is redirected to those in need and decrease food waste;
- Community-based research to engage citizens in participatory research projects;
- Sustainable tourism initiatives that create eco-friendly tourist accommodations built with bio-based materials.

Upper Austria

Upper Austria is characterized by rich potential in biomass products, with key value chains in bakery products, dairy products, oils, and brewery wastes. However, challenges exist, including the generation of avoidable food waste in the bakery products industry. Solutions below aim at overcoming these challenges and decrease food waste in the region:

- Food waste awareness campaigns to show responsible consumption and provide practical tips for minimizing food waste;
- Circular economy trainings for primary producers to explain its principles;
- Trust-building initiatives such as transparency in project outcomes and decision-making processes;

- Online platforms to utilize food waste where residents can share tips, recipes, and success stories related to reducing food waste.

Andalusia, Spain

Andalusia is rich in terms of olive and agricultural production, which stands as an important source of employment. The region has notable developments in the utilization of olive biomass for various applications, including energy production, composting, direct field application and extraction of high-value components. Following social innovation strategies align with the region's focus on utilizing olive biomass for energy generation, composting, and the extraction of high-value components:

- Circular bioeconomy awards and recognition programs to honor locals who actively practice circular bioeconomy principles;
- Cross-sector collaboration among agriculture, biotech, energy, cosmetics etc., to explore synergies and develop innovative solutions;
- Agrotourism initiatives that showcase the sustainable practices in the Andalusian circular bioeconomy.

7 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Social innovation represents a fundamental tool to boost rural bioeconomies. Being developed through a community-driven process, it considers the needs of all relevant stakeholders, including citizens and civil society. This leads to highlight barriers often overlooked by industrial stakeholders and policymakers. With society becoming more involved in innovation processes, businesses, technical institutions, and research organizations are no longer the only relevant agents. Citizens' empowerment becomes an important component. Customers and citizens are no longer just sources of information about needs; they also contribute more to the process of creating new products or services addressing their needs.

Collaboration and engagement with a variety of stakeholders are typical components of social innovation, which can also support sustainable development in terms of assisting in creating stronger, more resilient communities. Social innovation supports the development of more environmentally friendly business models, goods, and lifestyles as well as technology and procedures, promoting inclusive growth, and addressing global challenges such as climate change, energy scarcity, resource depletion, and food security. As a result, inequalities in society can be reduced and social inclusion can be encouraged, both of which are crucial elements of sustainable development. In this way, social innovation helps to combat social isolation and advance more environmentally friendly developments at the local level by encouraging collective well-being. This is made possible by satisfying the human need of connection with citizens involvement in social innovation projects. Social innovation can therefore give a strong contribution in generating a healthier society by involving citizens in collective projects, stimulating therefore their sense of connection and contribution.

Social innovation can be seen as a dynamic catalyst for positive change, a characteristic that is particularly crucial within the context of rural bioeconomies. Its versatility makes social innovation very attractive; indeed, it can be applied to a wide and diverse range of areas as shown in the description of the various types of social innovation

proposed in this handbook. Within the complex environment of bioeconomies, social innovation finds its implementation through a multifaceted approach. This encompasses strategies such as increasing social awareness and collaboration, exchanging good practices, applying circular economy principles to minimize waste, supporting sustainable agriculture and food systems, and utilizing renewable energy and biofuels. By sharing successful models and approaches, communities can learn from each other, accelerating the adoption of effective strategies.

This knowledge-sharing ecosystem plays a crucial role in navigating the complexities of rural bioeconomies and adapting solutions to local contexts. In this contest, stakeholders mapping is essential for ensuring a systematic and accurate identification of relevant needs to be covered by social innovation. Stakeholders mapping provides a structured approach to categorize and identify the relevant stakeholders, developing a solid understanding of their roles, relationships, and potential contributions. These stakeholders coming from a variety of sectors and backgrounds work together to create innovative solutions that address social problems and improve the well-being of individuals and communities.

Uptake of the bioeconomy is only possible with rural actors' contributions. Despite a large number of regionally accessible, underutilized biomass sources and a variety of promising recognition options, regional stakeholders are unable to fully realize the potential of the bioeconomy because they lack technical know-how, competitive networks, and market knowledge. Social innovation can create an environment where regional stakeholders, including private enterprises, government bodies, civil society organizations, and researchers, actively contribute to the development and expansion of innovative and sustainable bio-based value chains with the inclusion of citizens.

8 REFERENCES

- [1] Baker, S., & Mehmood, A. (2015). Social innovation and the governance of sustainable places. *The International Journal of Justice and Sustainability*, 20.
- [2] Benedetti, D. D. (2020). *Fuori dal Fango*. Mondadori.
- [3] European Commission. (2023). Social Innovation. Retrieved from https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/industry/strategy/innovation/social_en
- [4] European Commission. (2023). Rural development. Retrieved from Agriculture and rural development: https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/common-agricultural-policy/rural-development_en
- [5] Frost & Sullivan. (2015). Social Innovation in Energy Whitepaper. In Partnership with Hitachi, Ltd.
- [6] Nicholls, A., & Edmiston, D. (2018). Social Innovation Policy in the European Union. Policy Design in the European Union, 161-190. Retrieved from https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-64849-1_8
- [7] Olubunmi, O., Xia, P., & Skitmore, M. (2016). Green building incentives: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 1611-1621. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.01.028>
- [8] Ooms, M., Huygen, A., & Rhomberg, W. (2017). Social Innovation in Energy Supply: Summary Report.
- [9] Otto, I., Donges, J., Cremades, R., Bhowmik, A., Hewitt, R., Lucht, W., . . . Schellnhuber, H. (2020). Social tipping dynamics for stabilizing Earth's climate

- by 2050. PNAS, 2354-2365.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1900577117>
- [10] Park, H., & Grundmann, P. (2023). What does an inclusive bioeconomy mean for primary producers? An analysis of European bioeconomy strategies. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 225-241. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2022.2094353>
- [11] SCALE-UP Project. (2023). Overview of Regionally Suitable Solutions.
- [12] van der Have, R., & Rubalcaba, L. (2016). Social innovation research: An emerging area of innovation studies? *Research Policy*, 45.
- [13] Vierra, S. (2016). Green Building Standards and Certification Systems. Vierra Design & Education Services, LLC. Retrieved from https://globalgbc.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/034_green-building-standards-and-certification-system.pdf
- [14] Wang, W. (2022). Toward Economic Growth and Value Creation Through Social Entrepreneurship: Modelling the Mediating Role of Innovation. *Front Psychol.* doi:<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.914700>

9 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101060264.

The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.